

Impact of Excessive Screen Time on Social Skill Development of Primary School Children in Rural Field Practice Area of a Tertiary Care Centre, Kozhikode: A Cross Sectional Study

Krishna Raj J. S.¹, Rahana Raj R.², Arun V. J.³, Roshni S. S.⁴, Avani Pradeep⁵, Fathima Farhath C. P.⁶, Kannian Binub⁷, Prasily P.⁸

¹MD Community Medicine Department, Associate Professor, Malabar Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Calicut, India

²Postgraduate Community Medicine Department, Malabar Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Calicut, India

³MD Transfusion Medicine Department, Assistant Professor, Malabar Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Calicut, India

⁴MD Community Medicine Department, Assistant Professor, Malabar Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Calicut, India

⁵Intern, Department of community Medicine, Malabar Medical College Hospital and Research Centre

⁶Intern, Department of Community Medicine, Malabar Medical College Hospital and Research Centre

⁷MD Community Medicine Department, Professor, Malabar Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Calicut, India

⁸PhD Statistics, Community Medicine Department, Assistant Professor, Malabar Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Calicut, India

Received: 01-09-2025 / Revised: 16-10-2025 / Accepted: 08-11-2025

Corresponding Author: Dr. Roshni S. S.

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background: In our day-to-day life, screens have become an integral part. Children, in particular, are spending increasing amounts of time in front of screens, whether it's watching TV, playing video games, or scrolling through various social media. While screens can provide education, entertainment and social connection, excessive screen time has been linked to various negative effects on social skills development.

Objective: Aimed to investigate the impact of screen time on social skills development in Primary school children aged 6 to 11 years.

Material and Methods: A Cross sectional study was conducted at South AM UP School and Theruvathekadavu and GHSS Naduvannur in Rural Field Practice Area of Kozhikode district, Kerala from December 2024 to January 2025. A total of 220 children from both the schools were enrolled using stratified sampling. Screen time was categorized into three groups: Low (less than 1 hour per day), Moderate (1 to 3 hours per day), and High (more than 3 hours per day). Social skills were assessed using the Social Skills Improvement System (SSIS) Rating Scales. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, chi-square and Pearson correlation.

Results: The Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.864$) indicates a strong positive correlation screen time and social skill development problems.

Conclusion: High screen time is negatively associated with social skills development in young children. Limiting screen time may foster better social skills development.

Keywords: Screentime, Social Skill Development, Primary school children.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

In today's digital age, screen time has become an essential part of children daily lives through televisions, smartphones, tablets, and computers. While technology offers educational and entertainment benefits, excessive screen exposure has raised concerns regarding its impact on children's physical, mental, and social development. Also it has been linked to various negative effects on

social skills development such as social awkwardness, emotional struggles, social isolation, delayed emotional intelligence. The Global Screen Time Prevalence of Children aged 6-12 years is 4-6 hours per day on screens [1]. The Screen Time Prevalence in Indian children aged 6-12 years is an average of 3-4 hours per day on screens [2] Social skills include verbal and nonverbal communication,

such as speech, gestures, facial expression and body language. Social skill development is a vital aspect of a child's growth, enabling them to effectively interact, communicate, and build relationships with others. These skills are crucial for emotional intelligence, empathy, and conflict resolution [3]. When children spend more time interacting with screens than with humans, they miss out on essential social cues, such as facial expressions and body language. Increased screen time can lead to Social isolation, delayed emotional intelligence and Impaired communication skills.

Research suggests that excessive screen time can lead to social withdrawal, decreased emotional intelligence, and challenges in interpreting non-verbal cues. This study seeks to investigate the relationship between excess screen time and social skill development in children, exploring how reliance on digital communication may hinder their ability to engage in meaningful social interactions. The aim of the study is to assess the impact of excessive screen time on social skill development Of School Children aged 6-11 years In Rural Field Practice Area of a Tertiary Care Centre, Kozhikode

Materials and Methods

This observational study was conducted at grade 1 to grade 6 of South AM UP School, Theruvathekadave, Kozhikode (school 1) and GHSS Naduvannur, Kozhikode (school 2) over the period from December 2024 to January 2025.

Inclusion Criteria

School going children of 6 to 11 years in the designated school 2. Assent from the child.

Exclusion Criteria

- Those children who had no consent from parent. Simple Random Sampling was to done to select two schools from 22 schools under Balussery block using lottery method. The target population included children from first to sixth grade from the selected schools based on the study. The total population of the two schools was 515 (260 students in School 1 and 255 students in School
- The sample size was calculated using Cochran's formula

$$n_0 = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{e^2}$$

Where, Z= Z score (1.96 for 95% confidence interval) /P =Estimated proportion of children at risk (assume 0.5 for maximum variability) /e = Margin of error (typically 0.05 for 5%) resulting in an adjusted sample size of 220.

Stratified random sampling was used to select participants from each school. The students were

grouped into six classes (strata) based on their grade levels. Proportionate sampling was applied to determine the number of students from each stratum. Sample sizes for each grade were calculated proportionately, and the final sample sizes were rounded to the nearest whole number. Simple random sampling was used to select individual students, ensuring equal probability of selection throughout the process. Data obtained was entered in Microsoft office excel sheet 2016. This was then analysed using SPSS software version 20.0. Descriptive Statistics -Frequency and percentage were calculated for social skills scores and screen time scores. Inferential Statistics -Chi square was used to find out Association between screen time and social skill Development . Pearson correlation co-efficient was done to find out correlation between screen time and social skill development. The findings are presented in appropriate charts and tables.

A Pre-tested semi-structured questionnaire was administered to parents. A Pilot Study was conducted among 30 students. It was used to record the following information: socio-demographic characteristics like age, gender, education and other variables related to screen time and social skill development of children. Screen Time Questionnaire Scoring scale was used as a tool to assess Excessive screen time

Screening time scoring scale (3)

- 0-3 points: Low screen time
- 4-10 points: Moderate screen time
- 11-15 points: High screen time

Social skill improvement system rating scale

- 0-10 points: Healthy social skills and behaviour
- 11-20 points: Moderate risk of social skills and behavioral problems
- 21-30 points: High risk of social skills and behavioral problems
- 31-40 points: Severe risk of social skills and behavioral problems

Results

The demographic profile of our study is given in table (1) which shows slightly more female participants (56.8%) than males (43.2%). A majority of fathers (52.3%) and mothers (34.5%) had secondary education and 57.7% of fathers were unskilled workers. Nearly half of the participants (47.7%) belonged to socioeconomic class 5, while a few (2.3%) were in class 1. Screen Time Distribution of Study Participants were described in Fig (1) which shows 49 (22%) participants have low screen time and 90 (41%) participants have high screen time. Fig (2) describes Screen Time Risk of Study Participants which shows 146 (66%) participants were at screen time risk.

The Screen Time Distribution of Study Participants is given in Table (2) which shows most participants had moderate screen time (1–3 hours daily) across different activities. Screen time for TV/video watching, playing video games and non-educational usage are shown in Table (2) Distribution of Social Skill Development among Study Participants is given in Table (3) which shows most participants (33.6%) had healthy social skills and 15.5% at severe risk of social skills development. The Risk of Social Skill Development Problems among Study Participants is given in Fig (3) which concludes 120 (55%) participants are at risk of social skills development.

Association between Screen time and Social Skill Development Variables is given in Table (4) which shows statistically significant association between screen time and multiple aspects of social skill development problems, including empathy, cooperation, and communication ($p < 0.001$).

A strong positive association between Social Skill Problems and Screen time is given in Table (5)

Correlation between Screen Time and Social Skill Development problem is given in table (6) indicates a strong positive correlation between screen time and social skill development problems.

Table 1: Demographic overview of study Participants(N=220)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	95	43.2
	Female	125	56.8
Name of school	South AM UP School	112	50.9
	Naduvannur GHSS	108	49.1
Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	95	43.2
	Female	125	56.8
Name of school	South AM UP School	112	50.9
	Naduvannur GHSS	108	49.1
Educational status of Father	Illiterate	0	0
	Primary	6	2.7
	Secondary	166	75.5
	Undergraduate	44	20
	Postgraduate	4	1.8
Socio-economic status	Upper	5	2.3
	Upper middle	39	17.7
	Middle	22	10
	Lower middle	49	22.3
	Lower	105	47.7
Educational status of Mother	Illiterate	0	0
	Primary	2	0.9
	Secondary	142	64.5
	Undergraduate	74	33.6
	Postgraduate	2	0.9
Occupation of Father	Professional	1	0.5
	White collared job	13	5.9
	skilled worker	66	30
	Semi-skilled worker	11	5
	Unskilled worker	127	57.7
	Housewife	0	0
	Student	0	0
	Unemployed	2	0.9
Educational status of Father	Illiterate	0	0
	Primary	6	2.7
	Secondary	166	75.5
	Undergraduate	44	20
	Postgraduate	4	1.8
Socio-economic status	Upper	5	2.3
	Upper middle	39	17.7
	Middle	22	10
	Lower middle	49	22.3

Educational status of Mother	Lower	105	47.7
	Illiterate	0	0
	Primary	2	0.9
	Secondary	142	64.5
	Undergraduate	74	33.6
	Postgraduate	2	0.9
Occupation of Father	Professional	1	0.5
	White collared job	13	5.9
	skilled worker	66	30
	Semi-skilled worker	11	5
	Unskilled worker	127	57.7
	Housewife	0	0
	Student	0	0
	Unemployed	2	0.9

In our study 125 (56.8%) participants are female, and 95 (43.2%) participants are male. 112 (50.9%) participants are from SOUTH AM UP SCHOOL, while 108(49.1%) participants are from NADUVANNUR GHSS. In our study, majority of the participant’s father has secondary education 115(52.3%), while there are 4(1.8%) fathers who has post-graduation. In our study, majority of the participant’s mother has secondary education

76(34.5%), while there are 2(0.9%) mothers who has post-graduation. In our study, majority of the participant’s father’s occupation comes under unskilled worker category, 127(57.7%), while there are 2(0.9%) unemployed fathers. In our study, socio economic status of the majority of the participants comes under class 5 - 105(47.7%), while 5(2.3%) comes under class 1 (Table 1)

Figure 1: Screen Time Distribution of Study Participants (N=220)

In our study, 49 (22%) participants have low screen time, 81 (37%) participants have moderate screen time, 90 (41%) participants have high screen time (Fig 1)

Figure 2: Screen Time Risk of Study Participants (N=220)

Our Study Concludes that out of 220 participants, 146 (66%) participants are at screen time risk (Fig 2)

Table 2: Screen Time Distribution of Study Participants (N=220)

Screen Time Variable	Category	Screen Time Distribution	Frequency	Percentage
Daily Tv/ Video Watch Hours	Low Screen Time	< 1 Hour	77	35
	Moderate Screen Time	1-3 Hour	107	48.6
	High Screen Time	>3 Hour	36	16.4
Daily Hours of Video Game Playing	Low Screen Time	< 1 Hour	93	42.3
	Moderate Screen Time	1-3 Hour	103	46.8
	High Screen Time	>3 Hour	24	10.9
Non Educational Usage	Low Screen Time	< 1 Hour	84	38.2
	Moderate Screen Time	1-3 Hour	108	49.1
	High Screen Time	>3 Hour	28	12.7

In our study, majority of the participants, 107(48.6%) have moderate screen time (1-3 hours), 77 (35%) have low screen time (< 1 hour), 36 (16.4%) have high screen time (>3 hours) for daily tv / video watching .out of 220 participants, majority of the participants,103(46.8%) have moderate screen time (1-3 hours), 93 (42.3%) have low screen time (< 1

hour), 24 (10.9%) have high screen time (>3 hours) for playing video games daily. It is also evident that 108(49.1%) participants have moderate screen time (1-3 hours), 84 (38.2%) have low screen time (<1 hour), 28 (12.7) have high screen time for non-educational usage (Table 2)

Table 3: Distribution of Social Skill Development among Study Participants (N=220)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Social Skill Development	Healthy Social skill and behaviour	74	33.6
	Moderate risk of social skills and behavioural problems	67	30.5
	High risk of social skills and behavioural problems	45	20.5
	Severe risk of social skills and behavioural problems	34	15.5

Also in our study, majority of the participants 74(33.6%) have healthy social skill and behaviour and 34 (15.5%) have severe risk of social skills and behavioural problems (Table 3)

Figure 3: Risk of Social Skill Development Problems among Study Participants (N=220)

Our Study concludes that out of 220 participants, 120 (55%) participants are at risk of social skills developmental problems (Fig 3)

Table 4: Association between Screen time and Social Skill Development Variables

Variable	Category	Screen time		Chi Square/Fisher's Exact	p-value
		No	Yes		
Initiate conversation with peers	Always	51 (63.7%)	29 (36.3%)	67.4*	<0.001
	Often	16 (35.6%)	29 (64.4%)		
	Sometimes	7 (9.7%)	65 (90.3%)		
	Never	0 (0%)	23 (100%)		
Shows Empathy	Always	43 (72.9%)	16 (27.1%)	66.979*	<0.001
	Often	18 (38.3%)	29 (61.7%)		
	Sometimes	7 (11.7%)	53 (88.3%)		
	Never	6 (11.1%)	48 (88.9%)		
Work cooperatively in groups	Always	44 (69.8%)	19 (30.2%)	59.520*	<0.001
	Often	20 (30.8%)	45 (69.2%)		
	Sometimes	9 (12.9%)	61 (87.1%)		
	Never	1 (4.5%)	21 (95.5%)		
Resorts conflict with peers	Always	36 (58.1%)	26 (41.9%)	35.102*	<0.001
	Often	22 (42.3%)	30 (57.7%)		
	Sometimes	13 (16%)	68 (84%)		
	Never	3 (12%)	22 (88%)		
Non verbal communication	Always	37 (63.8%)	21 (36.2%)	30.863*	<0.001
	Often	16 (23.5%)	52 (76.5%)		
	Sometimes	14 (25%)	42 (75%)		
	Never	7 (18.4%)	31 (81.6%)		
Participate in group activities	Always	48 (58.5%)	34 (41.5%)	43.725*	<0.001
	Often	21 (25.3%)	62 (74.7%)		
	Sometimes	5 (15.2%)	28 (84.8%)		
	Never	0 (0%)	22 (100%)		
Express feelings appropriately	Always	46 (57.5%)	34 (42.5%)	36.272*	<0.001
	Often	13 (19.1%)	55 (80.9%)		
	Sometimes	14 (28%)	36 (72%)		
	Never	1 (4.5%)	21 (95.5%)		
Aware of social cues	Always	42 (64.6%)	23 (35.4%)	61.094*	<0.001
	Often	18 (50%)	18 (50%)		
	Sometimes	11 (15.3%)	61 (84.7%)		
	Never	3 (6.4%)	44 (93.6%)		

Our study demonstrates a statistically significant association between screen time and various domains of social skill development among the participants, as evidenced by the Chi-Square values and p-values (<0.001 across all variables).

Table 5: Association between Social Skill Problems and Screen time

Variable	Category	Social skill problems		OR (95% CI)	Chi-Square	p-value
		No	Yes			
Screen time	No	66 (89.2%)	8 (10.8%)	Reference	53.978	<0.001
	Yes	54 (37%)	92 (63%)	14.056 (6.271-31.502)		

Also study Shows Children with screen time were significantly more likely to have social skill problems compared to those without screen time (OR=14.056, 95% CI: 6.271–31.502, p<0.001) (Table 5)

Table 6: Correlation between Screen Time and Social Skill Development problem

		Excessive Screen time	Social Skill Development problem
Excessive Screen time	Pearson Correlation	1	.864**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	220	220
Social Skill Development problem	Pearson Correlation	.864**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	220	220

The Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.864$) indicates a strong positive correlation between screen time and risk of social skill and behavioural problems. (Fig 6)

Discussion

The aim of our study was to assess the impact of excessive screen time on social skill development Of School Children aged 6-11 years In Rural Field Practice Area of a Tertiary Care Centre, Kozhikode. In our study 125 (56.8%) participants are female, and 95 (43.2%) participants are male. 112 (50.9%) participants are from SOUTH AM UP SCHOOL, while 108(49.1%) participants are from NADUVANNUR GHSS. 105 (47.7) participants are from lower socio-economic status, which was similar to the study by Sharad Bansal[4]. In our study, majority of the parent's educational status were secondary education, which was contrast to the study conducted by sharad bansal, in which majority of the parents were having primary education[4]. Majority of the fathers, 127 (57.7) are unskilled workers which is in contrast to the study by Jenish Rajma, in which majority of the fathers had business as occupation[5].

Regarding the screen time distribution of our study participants, majority of the participants, 107(48.6%) have moderate screen time (1-3 hours), 77 (35%) have low screen time (< 1 hour), 36 (16.4%) have high screen time (>3 hours) for daily tv / video watching , which was similar to the study by Rajasekhar Reddy Munamala, in which out of 100 participants, 40 were having moderate screen time, 30 were having low screen time and 30 were having high screen time.[6]

Out of 220 participants, majority of the participants, 103(46.8%) have moderate screen time (1-3 hours), 93 (42.3%) have low screen time (< 1 hour), 24 (10.9%) have high screen time (>3 hours) for playing video games daily. In contrary to this, a study by Rubina Sulaiman shows, majority (88 participants) of them use smartphone to access youtube, while only 56 participants use smartphone to play video games.[7]

In our study it is also evident that 108(49.1%) participants have moderate screen time for non-educational usage which is similar to a study by sharad bansal, in which majority of the participants uses smartphone for non-educational purposes such

was listening to music, watching youtube, playing games[4].

Regarding the Social Skill Development of our study Participants the domains were empathy, cooperation, resolves conflict, anxious, initiates conversation with peers, responsibility, self-awareness, compromise which was similar to a study by Rajasekhar Reddy Munamala, in which the social skill domains were cooperation, assertion, responsibility, empathy and self-control [6]. In our study, out of 220 participants, majority of them 60 (27.3%) sometimes works cooperatively in groups, 60 (27.3%) participants sometimes shows empathy to others.

In our study, out of 220 participants, 41(18.6%) sometimes shows little anxious or withdrawn in social space. This was similar to a study done by Sharad Bansal in which out of 450 students ,182 (44.1%) participants were anxious due to the over usage of screen time[4].

In our study, out of 220 participants, majority of them 81 (36.8%) sometimes resolves conflict with peers. This was similar to the study conducted by Sharad Bansal in which, 30(7.3%) participants fights with friends and doesnt resolve it [4].

In our study, out of 220 participants, 23(10.5%) participants never initiate conversation with peers. This was similar to the study done by Rubina sulaiman, in which 59(26.5%) participants had impaired social relationship at school due to excessive screen time[7].

Overall, high screen time was significantly associated with poor development of multiple social skills which was similar to a study done by Sharad Bansal in which, they concluded that excessive screen time can have negative impact on physical, social and psychological development [4]. On contrary to this, a study by Sanjay Dixit concluded that the absence of screen time can result in loss of concentration and can create stress[8].

In our study, Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.864$) indicates a strong positive correlation between screen time and risk of social skill development which was similar to a study done by

Zedan Hu among 793 participants reported excessive screen time was significantly linked to peer interaction problems and poor social behavior [9]

Based on our study, which found a strong positive correlation ($r=0.864$, $p<0.001$) between high screen time and social deficits in children aged 6-11 years, we recommend that children be given a daily screen time of less than 1 hour in order to promote healthy social development. Schools and parents should encourage face-to-face interaction and structured activities to improve empathy, cooperation and conflict resolution skills, thereby reducing the risk of social isolation and delayed emotional intelligence.

Conclusion

This observational study, carried out among 220 primary school children aged 6 to 11 years in the rural Kozhikode district of Kerala, shows a strong negative correlation between excessive screen time and the development of social skills. Children with high levels of screen time (>3 hours per day) showed the greatest deficits in social skills, including empathy, cooperation, conflict resolution and non-verbal communication. Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.864$, $p<0.001$) shows a strong positive correlation between screen time and social skills problems in children exposed to screen time (OR = 14.056, 95-CI: 6.271-31.502). These findings concur with previous research highlighting the harmful effects of prolonged screen time on emotional intelligence and social interaction. In order to promote healthy social development, it is recommended to limit screen time to less than one hour per day. Measures aimed at educating parents and school programs promoting face-to-face interaction could reduce these risks and ensure better social outcomes for young children in the digital age.

Acknowledgements: The author would like to thank Foreign Medical Graduates posted in Department of community medicine, Malabar Medical College for helping in data collection.

Funding: The authors received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Availability of Data and Materials: Data will be available by emailing speaktodrkrishnaraj@gmail.com

Authors' Contributions

Krishna Raj J S is the Principal investigator of the study. He conceptualized the study, did a literature review, defined intellectual content, designed a survey, assisted data collection, analyzed and interpreted data, drafted the manuscript, reviewed, and edited. Rahana Raj R, Kannian Binub, Arun V J and Avani

Pradeep contributed to intellectual content, designed survey, helped in manuscript preparation, and reviewed the article. Prasily P and Fathima Farhath C P also analyzed, interpreted the data and contributed to conceptualization, designing. All authors substantially contributed to the study and collectively approved the final version of the manuscript.

Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate

Protocol, as set out by the Helsinki Declaration, was followed. Institutional ethics committee of Malabar Medical College Hospital and Research Center, Kozhikode, Kerala, India, approved the study in December 2024. (Ethics approval No. MMCH&RC/IEC/2024/12/01). The confidentiality of participants was maintained. Parents' consent was taken online, and Participants' Assent was taken before form submission.

Consent for Publication: Not applicable

Competing Interest: The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Open Access

This article is distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

(<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if changes were made. The Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication waiver (<http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>) applies to the data made available in this article unless otherwise stated

References

1. Cain, N., et al. (2010). Electronic media use and sleep in school-aged children and adolescents: A review. *Sleep Medicine*, 11(8), 735-742.
2. Kumar, S., et al. (2019). Screen time and physical activity in children aged 6-12 years: A cross-sectional study. *Indian Journal of Pediatrics*, 86(10), 931-936.
3. Muppalla SK, Vuppapalapati S, Pulliahgaru AR, Sreenivasulu H. Effects of Excessive Screen Time on Child Development: An Updated Review and Strategies for Management. 2023 Jun 18;15(6).
4. Bansal S, Mahajan RC. Impact of mobile use amongst children in rural area of Marathwada region of Maharashtra, India. *International Journal of Contemporary Pediatrics*. 2017 Dec 21;5(1):50.
5. Jenish Rajma, Krithikalakshmi Sathiyamoorthy, MBBS. Impact of Mobile Phones In Children's Lives and Factors

- Associated with Mobile Phone Addiction- A Prospective Observational Study. Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research). 2022 Sep 20.
6. Reddy Munamala R, Rafi S, Uma R. Impact of Screen Time On Social Skills Development In Young Children: An Observational Study. [cited2024Oct17]; Available from: https://academicmed.org/Uploads/Volume6Issue3/152.%20%5b3414.%20JAMP_PH%5d%20669-673.pdf.
 7. Sulaiman R, Shaji S, Sheela VV, Raheela AS. Mobile phone addiction among children aged 5-12 years, a hospital-based study in South Kerala. International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health [Internet]. 2021 Nov 24;8(12):5938–42.
 8. Dixit S, Shukla H, Bhagwat A, Bindal A, Goyal A, Zaidi A, et al. A study to evaluate mobile phone dependence among students of a medical college and associated hospital of central India. Indian Journal of Community Medicine. 2010;35(2):339.
 9. Hu Z, Bi S, Wang W, Liu C, Li L. Association of screen exposure with psychosocial problems in primary school students. Frontiers in Pediatrics. 2023 Jan 13;10.